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Preliminary Design of Turbojet Cruise Missiles

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Abstract: This paper presents a preliminary design study of three turbojet powered missiles whose main task is to cruise with medium subsonic speed, reach the maximum range at 60 km and terminally ram a moving target. Current modern cruise missiles fly at high subsonic speed which need powerful jet engine. Compensating the lack of such engine, our design's main feature lies in its ability to optimize the lift force at a spectrum of speed from 10 m/s to 30 m/s, with the lowest drag as possible as dictated for engagement against any static or moving ground target. Airfoil selection is tailored to assist a wing configuration design that could operate over than 20 m/s of speed spectrum. Main wing, fuselage, fins and leading edge wing extension or LERX are the main benefactors of a desired flight performance. A decent short period damping ratio and the ability to produce a tight vertical loop are major useful flight characteristics for the vehicle to track, follow and hit any ground target. Besides of a quick turning ability, a good handling quality is imperative for a manually controlled experimental flight. Lift, drag and moment analysis are conducted from data generated by CFD program such as FloEFD, and parametrical program such as Missile DATCOM. Those results are used to construct the airplane flight model and implement it in a non-linear flight simulator X-Plane. This flight model will be used to elaborate the preliminary design iteration further. It is observed that the designed vehicles, MOYAV Hiu (Shark) F14, F16 and F23 have preliminary flight performances that meet the design requirement.

Key Words: LERX wing, preliminary design, flight performance, flight dynamic, FloEFD, Missile Datcom, MOYAV Hiu series

Nomenclature

F_x, F_y	:force	R	:range
T	:thrust	V	:velocity
W	:weight	t	:time
D	:drag	γ	:path angle
L	:lift	θ	:pitch angle
g	:gravity coefficient	ω	:turning angle
q	:dynamic pressure	W_0	:initial weight
S_{ref}	:reference area	W_1	:final weight
I_{sp}	:specific impulse	SFC	:specific fuel consumption

1. Introduction

In any military air power arsenal, a cruise missile took a special place due to its advantages over conventional aircraft fighter or bomber. The main advantages are highlight usage of surprise element due to low exposure of the vehicle, reducing loss risk for aircrew, and one important factor is the combat range without refuel¹⁾.

In a dawn of a big conflict, cruise missile has the ability to conduct a large scale surgical strike opener by targeting the most heavily defended air-defense and radar system, which would be very costly if it is conducted by manned airborne assets. Nevertheless, few limitation of cruise missile exist such as the low-effectiveness of Terrain Contour Matching and DSMAC method to follow path and classifying target, respectively, in a hot desert environment where optical seeker has difficulty to sort out object. When tasked to find, track and target a moving vehicle, the cruise missile is also dealing with a burdening task, since main philosophy of its design shape is to reach any static target as far as possible. The remedy for the first problem is the usage of GPS to pinpoint the target, while tackling the second problem is considered more demanding, due to the conflicting reasons in determining many design factors.

Terminal maneuver takes third part of the whole flight phase regime, after boost phase and cruise phase consecutively. In the boost phase, a cylindrical form of shape is more desired, while in later phase an aircraft design characteristic specifically by using a large span wing is more suitable to conduct a cruising flight. In terminal phase, against any static target a simple rectangular wing plan form is quite sufficient to do the last maneuver which comprised mainly of diving maneuver. But for ramming a dynamic target which moves with a constant or non-linear motion, a more capable cruise missile with a revamped wing is needed. This is where this research heads on, based on previous research²⁾ finding a novel wing plan form design that has capability to maximize range and produce the most accurate hitting probability.

2. Problem Description

2.1. Design Philosophy and Goals

Designated as a proposal to the national cruise missile RKX-300TJ program owned by LAPAN, the MOYAV (Moyo-designed aerial vehicle) Hiu Series was intended to strike a moving target in a maximum possible range. The application of this vehicle would be offensive in nature, in which conventional aircrafts are still prohibited to deploy in a heavily defended installation target, such as mobile anti aircraft gun or patrolling ship. Fig. 2.1.1 shows many design of cruise missiles that fly in subsonic regime speed.

Fig. 2.1.1. Few Design of Subsonic Cruise Missiles

2.2. Design Requirements

A set of requirements was set for the MOYAV Hiu Series in order to accomplish mission effectively and efficiently. These requirements are:

Table 2.2.1. Air vehicle design requirement

Aspects	Requirement
• Payload	Warhead weighing 10 kg
• Avionics	IMU, GPS, Telemetry, Autopilot weighing 10 kg
• Dash	A 99 m/s dash in 15 minutes from launch time
• Range/Radius	60 km max to target or 30 km with 10 minutes loiter
• Power Thrust	40 kgf
• Take-off	Launched by rocket
• Cruise	Terrain Contour Mapping
• Termination	DSMAC Camera + GPS designated

2.3. Mission Profiles

2.3.1 Primary Mission: Strike a Static Target

The primary mission of the MOYAV Hiu Series is characterized by a mid-speed cruise to reach the target and a high-speed dive to hit the target. This mission is represented below.

Fig. 2.3.1.1. Primary mission flight sequence

Fig. 2.3.1.2. Secondary mission flight sequence

2.3.2. Secondary Mission: Patrol an area and Strike a Specific Moving Target

The secondary mission would be a combination of a cruise flight with a short loitering flight, to track, follow and ram a moving ground target.

2.4. Weight management

The maximum take-off weight chosen to be used by this vehicle design is about 50 kg, which include:

Table 2.4.1. Weight Allocation

Components	Weight
Wing	5 kg
Fuselage	5 kg
Control Surface	1 kg
Engine	4 kg
Payload	10 kg
Fuel + Tank	25 kg
Total	50 kg

According our previous experiments, external components such as launcher booster will take weight about 4 kg, with rail launch angle about 20 degrees, and underbelly booster installing angle about 20 degree³⁾.

2.5. Flight Condition

The flight conditions chosen for this study are desired to represent the condition where the air density is highest. Angle of attack and Mach number are carefully chosen for the following investigations of aircraft stability and maneuver simulation which are listed here in Table 2.5.1. The flight conditions for the investigation are equal to the conditions set in the virtual wind tunnel FloEFD and Missile DATCOM

so that the computed aerodynamic coefficients and derivatives could be validated by using non-linear flight simulator X-Plane version 10.45.

Table 2.5.1. Flight Condition Checkpoints

Altitude	0 m (sea-level)
Angle of Attack	-2 to 25 degree
Mach Number	0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5
Air Density	1.225 kg/m ³

3. Design Configuration Selection

3.1. Wing Plan form

In previous research, three types of plan form wing are considered for designing a cruise missile type aircraft, i.e rectangular, delta and hybrid²⁾. Rectangular plan form has the highest pitch rate number while delta has the lowest and hybrid stay in the middle. This research re explores this approach and investigate their impact to the profile mission. Three aircrafts are used as technical design insight, the F-16, F-14 and F-23 jet fighters.

3.1.1 Rectangular Wing: MOYAV Hiu F14

MOYAV Hiu F14 takes the Grumman F-14 wing plan form as concept for our first preliminary design variant. A pair of long rectangular main wing accompanied with two leading edge root extension (LERX) are the main benefactors for the aircraft's exceptional longitudinal agility. The location of the wing spar axis intersects the longitudinal body axis.

Fig. 3.1.1.1. MOYAV Hiu F14 and Grumman F-14¹⁶⁾

3.1.2. Hybrid Wing: MOYAV Hiu F16

General Dynamics/Lockheed Martin F-16 is *de facto* the leader of fighter aircraft in terms of maneuverability and agility⁴⁾. F-16 is not only highly maneuverable in longitudinal axis but also in lateral/directional domain. Similar to F-14, LERX is used to be coupled with main wing, but F-16's main wing has wider surface area (Sref) and resembling to a trapezoidal shape. MOYAV Hiu F16 takes this hybrid of the delta plan form of the LERX and the trapezoidal shape of main wing as the generator of lift. It is to be noted that the LERX is forward and rearward to widen the Sref area. The location of the wing is in the upper side of the fuselage.

Fig. 3.1.2.1. MOYAV Hiu F16 and GD/LM F-16¹⁷⁾

3.1.3. Trapezoidal Wing: MOYAV Hiu F23

A groundbreaking novel design is produced by Northrop Grumman when competing in ATF programme. The YF-23 uses trapezoidal wing plan form as a mean to produce lift as much as possible so that it will be deciding factor in extending the turn capability in a dogfight. LERX is not used in this design, but a special form type of control surface is adapted to mimick the F-23's large elevator surface. Wing location is inline with the main body axis.

Fig. 3.1.3.1. MOYAV Hiu F-23 and Northrop Grumman F-23¹⁸⁾

3.2. Aerodynamics Considerations

3.2.1. Airfoil Selection

We use airfoil NACA 6-series to produce wing section that has zero-alpha drag coefficient (C_{D0}) equal to 0.005 and reach $C_L = 1$ at $\alpha = 8$ degrees. Airfoil's max $C_L/C_D = 75$ could be achieved at angle of attack = 2.75 degrees. As shown in lower left of Fig. 3.2.1.1, the moment coefficient is inherently stable all the time. It is desirable that this airfoil can sustain the cruise missile at high subsonic speed regime.

Fig. 3.2.1.1 NACA 6-series Lift, Drag and Moment Polar⁵⁾

3.2.2. Wing Aerodynamic Coefficients

To compute the aerodynamic coefficients we use Missile DATCOM software, while to compute the aerodynamic forces we use a CFD program called Flo EFD. The condition point that we choose to validate the coefficients produced against a nonlinear flight simulator X-Plane is at sea-level altitude with velocity set at $M = 0.3$ or $U_{inf} = 100 \text{ m/s} = 357 \text{ km/h}$.

Table 3.2.2.1

Planform Wing	Sref	Sweep	CLalpha	CMalpha	AR=b/c
MOYAV Hiu F16	1.91	21.63	0.013	-0.02422	5.166667
MOYAV Hiu F14	1.585	21.4	0.019	-0.01874	5.740741
MOYAV Hiu F23	1.86	42.53	0.022	-0.00348	2.042857

Fig. 3.2.2.1. Wing's Lift Coefficients

Fig. 3.2.2.2. Wing's Drag Coefficients

Fig. 3.2.2.3. Wing's Lift-Drag Polar

Fig. 3.2.2.1. shows that MOYAV Hiu F23 has overall higher CL numbers than others. The omission of LERX and the large reference area Sref in F23-variant could contribute to the increase of CL alpha and CD alpha. Even though the F16-variant has largest Sref, but the existence of LERX could lower the CL alpha slope. Fig. 3.2.2.2. shows the disadvantage of the trapezoidal wing plan form, it has the highest CD alpha slope. Fig. 3.2.2.3. the CL to CD ratio shows that this trapezoidal wing plan form is suitable to be used for a cruising missile with low power thrust, while F16 and F14 needs higher power thrust. This graphic could be used for determining alpha angle needed to conduct cruise flight.

3.2.3. Static Stability

A good starting point to check any aircraft design stability is by taking a glimpse of its static margin characteristics. Assuming the location of center of gravity is fixed at $X_{cg} = 1.1365$ m for all variants, we can see that all three design are stable.

Fig. 3.2.3.1. MOYAV Hiu Series Static Margin comparison

The negative static margins show the designs' inherently static stable. F14 is the most static stable, while F23 has the weakest stability, but F16 static stability is volatile, i.e. stable only for positive angle of attack.

Fig.3.2.3.2. MOYAV Hiu Series Moment Characteristics

From moment graphics in Fig.3.2.3.2. we can find that the F23 variant has the poorest moment damping ratio, while F14 and F16 are comparable each other, nevertheless F14 variant is considered more conservative due to the resemblance with conventional aircraft flight characteristics in terms of moment.

3.2.4. Aerodynamics Forces and Moment

Missile DATCOM has quite good degree of validity for producing aerodynamics coefficient and derivatives at subsonic and supersonic speed regime, but in order to evaluate the forces and moments, CFD-software is to be used. FloEFD has ability to compute the forces and moments using an algorithm that is called Concurrent CFD. This approach combine CAD software's 3D modeling ability and the user-friendly interface to input required data or parameters to compute wind flow. The flow region is also wide (laminar, turbulent or even transitional) and it is switched automatically⁶⁾.

Fig. 3.2.4.1. MOYAV Hiu Series' Lift and Drag Forces and Lift over Drag Polar

From Fig. 3.2.4.1. (left and center), we can inspect that in terms of newton forces the F23 shows its uniqueness, although its CD numbers are found to be higher than other variant, but it seems the drag force result is reversed. This phenomenon could be explained by the downwash effect. Trapezoid shaped wing of F23 has tendency to produce smaller induced drag comparing to the higher aspect ratio wing or rectangular plan form. The F16 variant has high drag forces for large alpha angles, while the F14 has high drag forces for lower alphas and lowest drag for large alphas. F14 is also consistently has the lowest lift forces, F23 consistently has the highest and F16 is in the middle range.

Before angle of attack = 7 degree, the order of drag forces is $F23 < F16 < F23$. For lift forces, the F14 configuration seems has the lowest lift force that could be generated compared to other variants, this could be understood due to the lowest surface area of F14 wing.

From the lift over drag polar (Fig.3.2.4.1 right), by examining the first peak we can choose the optimum alpha for cruise is 5 degree for F23 variant, 4 degree for F16 variant and around 4 degree for F14 variant. Let's choose 4 degree as basis to compute Energy Management.

3.3. Longitudinal Flight Characteristic

Table 3.3.1. Moment of Inertia (kgm²)

Variant	Ixx	Iyy	Izz	Ixz
F23	2.72	34.94	36.5	0.12
F14	2.712	36.61	37.9	0.019
F16	2.8	38.56	40	0.066

From the table 3.3.1. we can quickly understand that the most inert vehicle in all axes of motion is the F16 variant, and the vehicle that has the most asymmetry in its geometry (XZ-plane) is the F23 variant.

Fig. 3.3.1. MOYAV Hiu Series short period damping ratio and natural frequency

Using moment of inertia characteristics, model mathematics for these three variants are yielded and from each flight condition checkpoints we deduce the Short Period damping ratio and natural frequency.

F14 seems to be the most dynamically stable with damping ratio more than 90%, and F16 is the fastest to conduct any pitch maneuver.

4. Flight Performance

4.1. Energy Management

From drag analysis, we produce the *available gradual energy* graphic. We can find the maximum speed that can be attained by each variant: ($V_{max}F23 = 0.35$) > ($V_{max} F14 = 0.325$) > ($V_{max}F16 = 0.32$). Between 0.1 and 0.3 Mach, the available energy is ideal to be used for cruising, while speed for Mach > 0.3 is ideal for dive maneuvering where the decrease of available energy can be compensated by increase of the kinetic energy.

Fig. 4.1.1 MOYAV Hiu series available gradual energy

Fig. 4.1.2 MOYAV Hiu series excessive lift

From lift analysis, we produce the excessive lift graphic. We can find the lowest speed achievable by each variant: ($V_{stall}F23=0.08$) < ($V_{stall}F16=0.11$) < ($V_{stall} F14=0.125$).

4.2. Range Performance

To find the maximum range that can be attained by the vehicles, Breguet range equation is used and derived here⁷⁾. $\sum Fx = 0, T - C_A S_{Ref} q - CN_\alpha \alpha^2 S_{Ref} q - W \sin \gamma = 0$.

From Newton's law above we can deduce the missile flight range as,

$$R = \int V dt \tag{1}$$

For a vehicle with diminishing fuel flow rate, the thrust is a product of mass flow rate and specific impulse.

$$T = \frac{dW}{dt} Isp \tag{2}$$

At trim condition, drag equals thrust and lift equals weight. Therefore

$$\frac{L}{D} = \frac{W}{T} \tag{3}$$

Arranging thrust to the right side,

$$T = \frac{W}{L/D} \tag{4}$$

Equating these thrust Eq. (2.) and (4.),

$$\frac{dt}{Isp} = \frac{dW}{W} (L/D) \tag{5}$$

By integrating this equation we can show the relation between time of flight and the change in aircraft weight, lift to drag ratio and specific impulse.

$$t = Isp (L/D) \ln\left(\frac{W_0}{W_1}\right) \tag{6}$$

for a jet powered aircraft, specific impulse is equal to the inverse of specific fuel consumption ($I_{sp} = 1/SFC$).

$$t = \frac{(L/D)}{SFC} \ln\left(\frac{W_0}{W_1}\right) \quad (7.)$$

Thus, one of the important factors in cruise missile range is the flight efficiency $V(L/D)$ ⁸⁾, which could be optimized to maximize range by decreasing thrust or fuel usage.

$$R = \frac{V(L/D)}{SFC} \ln\left(\frac{W_0}{W_1}\right) \quad (8.)$$

Where W_0 means initial gross weight, W_1 means final gross weight, V is for cruise velocity. SFC or specific fuel consumption for a typical jet engine with 40 kgf thrust, is computed and shown below in Fig.4.2.1

Fig. 4.2.1 Jetcat P-400 SFC

Fig. 4.2.2 Achievable Range of MOYAV Hiu Series

Therefore the range capability of MOYAV Hiu Series are computed using Eqn. (8) above. From Fig.4.2.2 graphic above we can see that the F23 variant is the most efficient in terms of cruising, so that according Breguet's Range equation F23 also has the farthest range achievable, and F16 has the lowest range capability.

4.3 Effect of Wing Planform to Pitch Rate

In longitudinal axis mode, pitch rate is an important factor for any aircraft to conduct pitching up maneuver such as loop or fast altitude following. The pitch rate depends on the wing plan form parameters, such as : wing loading, achievable alpha angle and C_L or C_N gradient.

$$\sum F_y = 0$$

$$\frac{L}{g} V \dot{\gamma} = q S_{ref} C_N - W \cos \gamma = 0 \quad (9.)$$

For an instantaneous vertical turn, the hypothetical vertical turn radius will become

$$R_v = \frac{V}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (1)$$

While for a sustained horizontal turn, the hypothetical horizontal turn radius will become

$$R_h = \frac{2W}{g C_N S_{ref} \rho} \quad (11.)$$

Substituting $C_N = C_{N_\alpha} \alpha + C_{N_\delta} \delta$ into (9) and dividing by $\frac{W}{g} V$, the pitch rate is found to be

$$\dot{\gamma} = g \frac{n}{V} = \frac{q S_{ref} (C_{N_\alpha} \alpha + C_{N_\delta} \delta) - W \cos \gamma}{\frac{W}{g} V} \quad (12.)$$

With assumption angle of attack is 30 degrees, the pitch rate computation is presented into a turn rate envelope. This graphic is useful to find their corner speed characteristics.

Fig.4.3.1 Turn Rate Envelope of MOYAV Hiu Series

From Fig.4.3.1., we can see that F23-variant has the most capable to produce fast instantaneous turn rate (8 deg/s) and high sustained turn rate ($\dot{\omega}$ or $\dot{\psi}$), while the F14-variant has the weakest capability in turn performances (3 deg/s). F16 is not a weak choice since turn rate = 6 deg/s is comparable to F23.

5. Simulation

Using previous researches' non-linear flight simulation environment ⁹⁾ and previous procedure to test the accuracy of hitting any target ¹⁰⁾, results presented below are extracted from the following engagement scenarios. The aircrafts are conducting terminal phase maneuvers, i.e. after enduring cruise phase and entering target zone the aircraft start to climb until reaching 500 meters above it, subsequently two immediate other options are presented. First, the aircraft is set to follow a target point which is situated 1000 meter in front of the apogee point. Second, the aircraft immediately dive once the apogee point is reached.

Fig. 5.1. Dive Bombing Maneuver Results

Fig. 5.2. Sudden Stop Dive Bombing Results

The red-dotted line is from F14-variant's trajectory, the blue-linear one is from MOYAV Hiu F23, while the green-dashed line is from MOYAV Hiu F16. Both graphics show similar results, in terms of range F16 needs the shortest distance to hit a target, while the F23 needs the longest. F14 pitching up capability is remarkable, despite the previous computation of turn rate that shows F14's low number of pitch rate, but in terms of climbing performance, F14 excels others by being the only one which can reach 500 meters altitude thus providing the highest Kinetic Energy Impact. F16 shows some unique flight characteristics at the sudden stop dive bombing, where its trajectory shows that the missile make a very sharp vertical turn so that its direction goes rearward. The F23 variant impact the target with a straight linear glide slope at Fig. 5.1. i.e. miss distance will be minimum, whereas other variants show a tendency to pitch at the last moment.

6. Conclusions

This paper investigates the effect of wing plan form to range performance, pitch rate/turn rate performance, dive bombing range, dive bombing height and diving speed. MOYAV Hiu F23 is clearly shown that its trapezoidal wing facilitates it to be the most range efficient, but not so useful for diving bombing which need high altitude and shortest time yet fastest to hit the target. MOYAV Hiu F14 although shows unconvincing number in the aerodynamic coefficients, but it seems very powerful when it is tasked to dive bombing. F14 can reach the highest altitude and deliver the biggest energy kinetic at impact. F16 maybe is the weakest performer in all contested area (range, pitch rate, altitude and energy impact) which is mainly due to contribution of high moment inertial characteristics, but because of its inherent stability F16 could produce more accurate results, reflected by the shortest range needed to conduct dive bombing which also can reduce wind disturbance.

We can conclude that rectangular wing (F14) is more suitable for cruise missile preliminary design in terms of energy kinetic hit impact, while the hybrid wing (F16) could be chosen to yield more accurate impact. Although the trapezoidal wing of F23 seems very beneficial to expand the range to maximum but the flight characteristics could be exploited very well for a future UCAV (unmanned combat air vehicle). After freezing main aerodynamics and performance characteristics of these turbojet powered cruise missile configurations, next research's focus could be posed on the miss distance and control optimization on how to reduce it.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to recognize the LAPAN's long term rocketry national program which enables this research to be conducted to strengthen national capability in aerospace vehicle design especially in high-speed 6-DOF flight dynamics. To Mr. Herma Yudhi Irwanto, thank you for authorizing me to design this marvelous flight vehicle.

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